

THE ESSENCE OF PHILOSOPHICAL IDEAS IN BERDAK'S POEMS

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Annotation: This article discusses in detail the essence of philosophical ideas in Berdak's poems, living conditions, the socio-political life of the people on all examples of Berdak's works, the study of the life and work of Berdak, the great representative of the Karakalpak literature.

Key words: philosophical ideas, creatures, artistic or moral creativity, attitude towards creativity.

Introduction:

Berdak, the son of Kargaboy, in the 19th century in Burma, a poet who made a great contribution to the development of socio-political, religious, philosophical and artistic and moral thinking in the region, witnessed the invasion of Georgian socio-philosophical and artistic and moral characteristics, became witnessed the invasion of the colonialists and saw firsthand the will of the mustabid system and was one of the most influential figures in our people, reflecting this historical history in the world, creativity and heritage.

Literature analysis and methodology:

Berdak was born into an educated, enlightened family, after graduating from the old school, he received an oriental education in the Karakum Eshon madrasah in the modern Moinak region. While studying at the madrasah, he independently replenished his knowledge, studied historical stories, legends, the genealogy of the Turkic peoples, tribal symbols, Karakalpak folklore, customs, traditions and rituals, and culture on a large scale.

The traditions of oriental history, the art and works of the Khorezm historians Munis, Ogakhi, as well as the ideas of the Yassavi and Nakshbandi sects had a great influence on the artistic and moral creativity, worldview, especially the historical views of Berdak. The theme of the epic historical works "Avlodlar", "Omongeldi", "Ernazarbi" are the ideas of independence, the national liberation struggle.

Deep respect for grandmother Berdak, sacred trust, professional pride and at the same time a protest against economic and social oppression, the enlightened people of Khiva, Urgench, schools and madrasahs that have a system of knowledge, culture and education for Uzbeks. , Karakalpak and Turkmen peoples Critical remarks are expressed in brighter lines.

According to Berdak, the essence and purpose of human life is to be loyal to one's people and show selflessness in the name of the development of the Motherland. In the works of Berdak, encouraging young men to do good deeds, he emphasizes that the unity of the people is the main tool for achieving higher goals.

Berdak is a great folk singer, able to convey to the reader the pain and suffering of a sensitive poet, as well as to give warmth, which is a balm from the grassy pain of the people. The poet, who understood this well, wrote poems with special emphasis on notes, which the reader

must pay attention to in order to gain knowledge, referring to the essence of experiences in his poems.

Results:

The time of Berdak was not only a time of conflict, but also a time full of hardships and hardships. This can be seen not only in the songs of the poet Berdak, but also in all the works of his creative activity. It was also written in manuscripts by Cordini, Zamonda, Panohber, Akibat, Davru davran, Kozim, Bolmadi, Ayrimak and others.

In all the works of Berdak, one can get a complete picture of the living conditions of the people, the social and political life of that time. In his works, the poet tried to console the people with his songs about the plight of the people, poverty. Berdok's work "Avlodlar" is a chronicle of historical events, general events in the life of the Karakalpaks and other Turkic peoples are recorded, various opinions about the origin of tribes and peoples are described.

Discussion:

Berdak exposed the misdeeds of some of the prominent priests of his day in his poems such as "Yakarikar" and "Shekilli" and wrote many editions in his other writings. He defends the rights of women, encourages young people to love their Motherland and reach the heights of enlightenment.

To do this, if we translate the poems of Burdock's life and work from the works of our writers into other languages in order to attract the younger generation to our whirlwind with the ideas of creativity in its epics, the pursuit of science, serving the people, then the youth of our multilingual nation will read it.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it should be said that Shavkat Mirziyoyev, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Life itself has repeatedly proved that without advanced science it is impossible to build a free and prosperous society in any country. In all the works of writers of the past and present, it is emphasized that the chain connecting the past and the future passes through a high level of cognitive potential of young people and an advanced level of knowledge in all areas in our turbulent and rapidly changing present time..

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